

**ADDITIONS TO THE MYCOLOGICAL CATALOGUE
OF MADEIRA ARCHIPELAGO (PORTUGAL).
RECORDING OF 21 NEW TAXA**

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Summary. JARDIM, P. & C. LOBO (2024). Additions to the mycological catalogue of Madeira archipelago (Portugal). Twenty-one new records. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 48: 105-116.

As a result of the study of the fungi collected in Madeira island during the year 2023, we propose the following taxa as new records for the Madeiran mycological catalogue. *Basidiomycota* (19): *Agaricus moelleri*, *Calocera cornea*, *Chaetocalathus craterellus*, *Crepidotus carpaticus*, *C. crocophillus*, *C. flammeus*, *Cyclocybe aegerita*, *Cystolepiota pulverulenta*, *C. seminuda*, *Lactarius quietus*, *Leucoagaricus vassiljevae*, *Marasmiellus candidus*, *Mycena arcangeliana*, *M. corynephora*, *Polyporus tuberaster*, *Rimbachia neckerae*, *Russula parazurea*, *Steccherinum ochraceum* and *Tomentella crinalis*; *Ascomycota* (1): *Humaria hemisphaerica*; *Myxomycota* (1): *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa*.

Key words: Fungi, morphology, taxonomy, ecology.

Resumen. JARDIM, P. & C. LOBO (2024). Adiciones al catálogo micológico del archipiélago de Madeira (Portugal). Registro de 21 nuevos táxones. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 48: 105-116.

Como resultado del estudio de los hongos recolectados en Madeira durante el año 2023, hemos recopilado los siguientes nuevos táxones para el catálogo micológico de Madeira. *Basidiomycota* (19): *Agaricus moelleri*, *Calocera cornea*, *Chaetocalathus craterellus*, *Crepidotus carpaticus*, *C. crocophillus*, *C. flammeus*, *Cyclocybe aegerita*, *Cystolepiota pulverulenta*, *C. seminuda*, *Lactarius quietus*, *Leucoagaricus vassiljevae*, *Marasmiellus candidus*, *Mycena arcangeliana*, *M. corynephora*, *Polyporus tuberaster*, *Rimbachia neckerae*, *Russula parazurea*, *Steccherinum ochraceum* and *Tomentella crinalis*; *Ascomycota* (1): *Humaria hemisphaerica*; *Myxomycota* (1): *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa*.

Palabras clave: Hongos, morfología, taxonomía, ecología.

INTRODUCTION

The first references to fungal species in Madeira island date back to the first half of the 19th century (HOLL, 1830), although more comprehensive mycological studies only began in the early 20th century by TORREND (1909, 1912, 1913), with the description of 338 new species for the Madeiran Archipelago. Following these initial studies, further

extensive research mostly focused on phytopathology, as well as the *Ascomycota* of Macaronesia, lead to the finding and description of more fungal species, with emphasis on the publications of VIENNOT-BOURGIN (1939) and KORF (1978, 1981a,b, 1992), respectively. Subsequent studies by CALONGE & MENEZES DE SEQUEIRA (2003, 2007) and CALONGE & SILVA (2006) referenced 281 species, mostly belonging to the *Basidiomycota*. In

2008, a compilation and revision of all these findings resulted in a checklist of 743 fungal species for Madeira Archipelago (MELO & CARDOSO, 2008). Occasional follow-up studies have added new species to this record, including the description of a new endemic species to Madeira island (CALONGE & *al.*, 2008–2013; CALONGE & MENEZES DE SEQUEIRA 2011a,b). More than a decade has passed without any further extensive updates to the mycological catalogue of Madeira archipelago. As a result of the study of fungi collected in Madeira island during 2023, we propose the inclusion of 21 species to the mycological catalogue of Madeira Archipelago.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The collection, processing and storage of fungal specimens were carried out for the most part following the guidelines for collecting fungi to the fungarium published by the Natural History Museum of Oslo (NHM, 2022). Species identification was done using fresh specimens. Macro and microscopic features were analysed using a microscope (Zeiss Stemi 2000) and a bright field microscope (Olympus CX22LED). Most photos of the analysed specimens were taken using a Cannon powershot G6 camera. Biometric measurements of spores or other microscopic characteristics relevant for identification were obtained through the observation and measurement of at least 10 units. Taxon nomenclature and author abbreviations follow the Myco bank database (<https://www.mycobank.org/>). All studied material is stored in the herbarium of the Jardim Botânico da Madeira Eng. Rui Vieira botanical garden (MADJ-F).

STUDIED MATERIAL

Basidiomycota

Agaricus moelleri Wasser (Fig. 1)

A couple of specimens of this species were found in Fajã da Nogueira, growing on soil on the edge of a forest trail, IX–2023. MADJ-F-195.

Fig. 1. *Agaricus moelleri* Wasser. Basidiocarps.

Cap 4–10 cm wide, initially globose becoming broadly convex at maturity. Cap flesh white, turning instantly yellow when bruised, covered in grey appressed scales which are densest towards the cap centre. Gills typical of the genus, pink, crowded and free. Stipe up to 10 cm long, white, turning instantly yellow when handled, with a ring. Spores $4.5\text{--}6.5 \times 3\text{--}4 \mu\text{m}$. The odour is carbolic, resembling fresh ink.

Observations: *Agaricus moelleri* can be easily mistaken with *A. xanthodermus*, of which it was once a variety, but the minute grey coloured appressed scales on the cap surface distinguish it of this species (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 509).

Calocera cornea (Batsch) Fr. (Fig. 2)

Fruiting bodies found in Chão da Ribeira, growing either scattered or in clusters on barkless dead wood of *Ocotea foetens*, IX–2023. MADJ-F-158.

Basidiocarps cylindrical and waxy, bright orange, up to 2 cm tall, mostly unbranched and acute, darker towards the base and sometimes with a short stem. The basidia are typical of the order

Fig. 2. *Calocera cornea* (Batsch) Fr. Basidiocarps.

Dacrymycetales, fork shaped and 2-spored. Spores $8-10 \times 3-3.5 \mu\text{m}$, with one septum.

***Chaetocalathus craterellus* (Durieu & Lév.) Singer.** (Fig. 3)

Many basidiocarps of this species were found in Chão dos Louros, fructifying on almost every decaying twig in damp places, V1–2023. MADJ-F-55.

Basidiocarp pleurotoid, cap white to cream, up to 2 cm across, extremely tomentose due to long, thick walled hairs, which makes it somewhat tough. Lamellae well-developed, white to cream. Stipe absent. Spores smooth and ellipsoid, $7-9 \times 5-6 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: Drought tolerant species, also collected in Chão da Ribeira (V–2023) and Ribeiro frio (VI–2023), where numerous basidiocarps were found. Apparently locally common and probably more widespread across Madeira.

***Crepidotus carpaticus* Pilát.** (Fig. 4)

Numerous crowded fruitbodies of this species were found in Levada Velha do Plano (Ginjas),

Fig. 3. *Chaetocalathus craterellus* (Durieu & Lév.) Singer. Basidiocarps.

Fig. 4. *Crepidotus carpaticus* Pilát. Basidiocarps.

on a living stem of *Sonchus fruticosus*, X–2023. MADJ-F-239.

Cap fan-shaped, up to 1.5 cm wide, white to yellowish in younger specimens, becoming brownish with age but retaining a paler margin. The upper part of the cap is often distinctively tufted, concolorous with the cap and sometimes connecting to the substrate. The gills, just like the cap, are first

Fig. 5. *Crepidotus crocophyllus* (Berk.) Sacc. Basidiocarps.

yellowish, becoming brownish at maturation, with a very pale edge. Stem absent to very short. Spores globose, finely echinulate, 5–6.5 μm .

***Crepidotus crocophyllus* (Berk.) Sacc. (Fig. 5)**

Mature basidiocarps were found growing in Ribeiro Bonito on dry decomposed wood of *Ocotea foetens*, IV–2023. MADJ-F-96.

Cap shell-shaped, 1–3 cm across, densely covered with dark brown scales on a pale brownish background. Gills pale orange, frequently incomplete, with dark brown scales (identical to those present in the cap) only near the point of attachment to the substrate. Stem absent. Spore print brown. Spores spherical, finely ornamented, 5–7 μm .

Observations: This species can be confused with *Crepidotus calolepis* which lacks the distinctive orange gills (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 94).

***Crepidotus flammeus* Murrill. (Fig. 6)**

≡ *Pleuroflammula flammea* (Murrill) Singer.

In Chão da Ribeira, basidiocarps of this species were found developing solitarily or in small groups on deadwood of *Ocotea foetens*, mostly in damp, dark places of the Laurel forest, VI–2023. MADJ-F-173.

Cap mussle-shaped up to 1 cm wide, yellow with irregular ferruginous orange scales, dentate

Fig. 6. *Crepidotus flammeus* (Murrill) Singer. Basidiocarps.

at the margin from the triangular remnants of the veil which often become absent at maturity. Gills orange, with a distinct paler margin. Stem white to yellowish, lateral, rarely absent, up to 0.5 cm long, with a fibrillose yellow to orange ring. Pleurocystidia absent, spores 7.8–10 \times 5–6 μm .

Observations: Although the absence of pleurocystidia separates this species from *Pleuroflammula ragazziana* (HORAK, 1978), the spore dimensions of the studied material are closer to the larger spore size of *P. ragazziana*.

***Cyclocybe aegerita* (V. Brig.) Vizzini. (Fig. 7)**

= *Agrocybe aegerita* (V. Brig.) Singer.

= *Pholiota aegerita* (V. Brig.) Quél.

Fascicules of fully mature basidiocarps were found growing on buried decaying wood at the Jardim Botânico da Madeira Eng. Rui Vieira botanical garden, IX–2023. MADJ-F-162.

Cap up to 15 cm wide, pale buff at the centre but gradually fading to white towards the margins, without radial structure. Gills brownish, adnate, but sometimes running down the stem. Stem fleshy, 4–9 cm long, white, with some brownish spots corresponding to spore deposition, along with a persistent ring. Flesh cream, with a pleasant odour.

Fig. 7. *Cyclocybe aegerita* (V. Brig.) Vizzini. Basidiocarps.

Spore print light brown. Spores smooth and ellipsoid, $8\text{--}11 \times 5\text{--}6 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: Choice edible species, also referred under the name *Cyclocybe cylindracea*.

Cystolepiota pulverulenta (Huijsman) Vellinga. (Fig. 8)

Two fully mature fruiting bodies were found in Chão da Ribeira, growing on rich soil in a dense vegetation cover of Laurel Forest, VI–2023. MADJ-F-108.

Cap pale, 2–4 cm across, convex, extremely scaly powdery, with the powder quickly turning cinnamon brown with age or when handled. Gills white, moderately crowded and free. Stipe 4–7 cm long, covered with the same powdery elements present on the cap. Spores smooth, $4\text{--}5 \times 2.5\text{--}3.5 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: A very rare species in temperate Europe and probably also in Madeira. *Cystolepiota seminuda* is a close species, but is less fleshy and without instantly browning scales (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 325).

Fig. 8. *Cystolepiota pulverulenta* (Huijsman) Vellinga. Basidiocarps.

Cystolepiota seminuda (Lasch) Bon. (Fig. 9)

Mature basidiocarps were found in Fajã da Nogueira, on rich soil in a mixed Laurel forest with *Castanea sativa* and *Quercus spp.* IX–2023. MADJ-F-213.

Cap convex, chalk white to pinkish, up to 2 cm across, powdery, with a clearly dentate cap margin from the partial veil. Gills white and free, often with short gills. Stem very slender, 1–2 mm wide and 3–5 cm tall, covered with the same powdery elements of the cap. The stem powder disappears in older specimens to reveal a pinkish to redish stem. Spores smooth, $3.5\text{--}4.5 \times 2\text{--}2.5 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 9. *Cystolepiota seminuda* (Lasch) Bon. Basidiocarp.

Fig. 10. *Lactarius quietus* (Fr.) Fr. Basidiocarps.

Observations: Other *Cystolepiota* species are much fleshier, which makes this species easy to identify (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019:324).

***Lactarius quietus* (Fr.) Fr. (Fig. 10)**

Multiple fully mature basidiocarps were found in Fajã da Nogueira, developing in association with *Quercus* spp. on a range of different soil types, IX–2023. MADJ-F-201.

Cap 4–8 cm wide, convex, brownish-red with faint concentric zones, sometimes covered with a white dust in younger specimens. Gills unequal, crowded, whitish, adnate to slightly decurrent, developing brownish stains at maturity. Stipe 5–10 cm long, whitish near the cap but becoming darker towards the base. Flesh whitish, with a stink-bug like smell. Milk whitish to cream, immutable, somewhat watery. Spores ornamented, $6-9 \times 5-7 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: The edibility of this species is disputed, mainly due to its unpleasant smell. *Lactarius chrysorrheus* is a similar species and also occurs with *Quercus* spp. trees, but it is generally paler and the milk turns almost instantly sulphur-yellow upon cut (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 432).

Fig. 11. *Leucoagaricus vassiljevae* E.F. Malysheva, Svetash. & Bulakh. Basidiocarps.

***Leucoagaricus vassiljevae* E.F. Malysheva, Svetash. & Bulakh. (Fig. 11)**

Mature basidiocarps were found in Chão da Ribeira, dispersed on rich soil in the Laurel forest, IX–2023. MADJ-F-144.

Cap 4–6 cm wide, convex to applanate, with orange-brown to somewhat pinkish radial fibrils on a pale background, with a darker, evenly coloured central umbo. Gills free and white. Stipe up to 7 cm long, pale, with a white, easily detachable ring close to the cap. The flesh is white, delicate, with no distinctive odour. Spores smooth, amygdaliform, $7-8 \times 4-5 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: Although this species is morphologically very similar to *Leucoagaricus rubrotinctus*, it can be identified by the distinctive amygdaliform basidiospores (MALYSHEVA & *al.*, 2013).

***Marasmiellus candidus* (Fr.) Singer. (Fig. 12)**

Several basidiocarps of this species were found in Ribeiro Bonito, growing gregariously on twigs and small logs under a range of native trees and shrub species, VI–2023. MADJ-F-100.

Cap convex to broadly convex with age, smooth, 0.5–2 cm across, either completely white or

Fig. 12. *Marasmiellus candidus* (Fr.) Singer. Basidiocarps

with some brownish tinges. Gills slightly decurrent, whitish to pinkish, distant, becoming venose near the cap margin. Stipe 0.4–1 cm long, smooth, initially equally white, then usually developing a dark tomentum from the base upward. Spores smooth, ellipsoid, $12\text{--}18 \times 4\text{--}6 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: This species was also found in Chão da Ribeira (IX–2023).

***Mycena arcangeliana* Bres. (Fig. 13)**

Numerous basidiocarps of this species were found in Chão da Ribeira growing in clusters on decomposed wood from a range of native tree species, IX–2023. MADJ-F-172.

Cap conical, becoming campanulate with age, up to 4 cm in diameter at maturation. The cap is olivaceous-green when young, soon becoming

Fig. 13. *Mycena arcangeliana* Bres. Basidiocarps.

featureless with whitish to greyish colours at the cap centre, margin striate. Gills adnexed, white, becoming pinkish with age, with characteristic cheilocystidia covered by cylindrical excrescences. The stipe is dark grey, 3–6 cm long, with distinctive long, rigid, white hairs at the base. The flesh has a very unique strong smell of iodoform. Spore print white, spores ellipsoid, $8\text{--}9 \times 4\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: The combination of strong iodoform smell, the cheilocystidia covered by cylindrical excrescences and the stipe base covered in long, rigid white hairs should make this species hard to misidentify (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 220).

***Mycena corynephora* Maas Geest. (Fig 14)**

Found in Encumeada, growing in small colonies on humid moss covered bark of deadwood, VIII–2023. MADJ-F-142.

Cap white, 0.2–0.6 cm wide, very powdery, campanulate to convex and with a striate margin. Lamellae adnate and white. Stipe concolorous with the cap, up to 1 cm long, finely striate and downy from caulocystidia. Basal disc absent, but sometimes thickened basally. Spores spherical to subglobose, $6\text{--}10 \times 6\text{--}8 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 14. *Mycena corynephora* Maas Geest. Basidiocarps.

Observations: Locally common but probably overlooked due to its minute size. *Mycena tenerri-ma* is a similar species but has a grainy rather than powdery cap and a distinct basal disc (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019:208).

Polyporus tuberaster (Jacq. ex Pers.) Fr. (Fig. 15)

Two basidiocarps of this species were found in Ribeiro Bonito, maturing on a humid fallen branch of *Ocotea foetens*, VI–2023. MADJ-F-104.

Cap up to 3.5 cm wide, round and slightly depressed at the center, light brown to whitish near the fimbriate margin, covered by erect brown scales. Pores white, deeply decurrent, 1–2 per mm, irregular but mostly oblong. Stipe up to 3 cm long, pale above but becoming brownish near the base, attached to the substrate through dark, tube like pseudosclerotia. Spores cylindrical, $11\text{--}16 \times 4\text{--}6 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: This species can differ greatly in fruitbody size, reaching up to 14 cm in cap diameter in some individuals. This variation is normally correlated with the size of the substrate (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 834).

Fig. 15. *Polyporus tuberaster* (Jacq. ex Pers.). Basidiocarps and detail of the deeply decurrent pores.

Rimbachia neckerae (Fr.) Redhead. (Fig. 16)

Many individuals of this species were found in Encumeada, growing on a root of *Erica arborea* densely covered with bryophytes. Basidiocarps were parasitizing plants of the foliose liverwort *Lejeunea eckloniana*. VI–2023. MADJ-F-78.

Basidiocarps cypheloid, white, very small (aprox. 1 mm wide), finely felty, with a smooth, almost translucent hymenophore. The fruitbody is connected to the liverwort through a white

Fig. 16. *Rimbachia neckerae* (Fr.) Redhead. Basidiocarps.

neck-like pseudostipe that can measure up to 2 mm long. Spores ellipsoid, $7\text{--}11 \times 5\text{--}7 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: A rarely recorded species in temperate Europe but probably overlooked due to its minute size and restricted ecology. Although we discovered this species associated to a foliose liverwort, it is typically found parasiting pleurocarpous mosses (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 1078).

Russula parazurea Jul. Schäff. (Fig. 17)

Small groups of basidiocarps of this species were found in Lamaceiros, developing on the soil along a trail under *Quercus sp.* or *Fagus sp.* trees, which were scattered on an area with native vegetation, IX–2023. MADJ-F-187.

Cap convex to slightly depressed in older individuals, 4–9 cm wide, bluish-green to grey, powdery. Gills adnexed, complete and somewhat fragile. Stipe white and cylindrical, 4–7 cm long, snapping like chalk to reveal a pale, mild tasting flesh, with no distinctive odour. Spore print cream, spores covered with warty ornaments, $6\text{--}8 \times 5\text{--}7 \mu\text{m}$.

Observations: Very similar to *Russula grisea* but distinguished by the pruinose and rather

Fig. 17. *Russula parazurea* Jul. Schäff. Basidiocarps.

Fig. 18. *Steccherinum ochraceum* (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) Gray. Basidiocarp and detail of the hymenium.

monochrome bluish-green cap (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019: 384). Older specimens may lose the pruinose feature, thus it is recommended to collect and study basidiocarps in early stages of development.

Steccherinum ochraceum (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) Gray. (Fig. 18)

Basidiocarps of this species were found on dead wood at Chão da Ribeira, growing gregariously and featuring both resupinate and pseudo-capped shapes, IX–2023. MADJ-F-184.

Basidiocarp orange, up to 2 cm wide and with a paler margin. The fertile surface is composed of crowded, wide, orange and tooth like spines, measuring up to 0.2 cm in length. When present, the capped surface is yellowish and with a cream margin. It has characteristic long, thick-walled cystidia, covered by crystals on the upper part. Spores smooth, $3\text{--}4 \times 2\text{--}2.5 \mu\text{m}$.

Tomentella crinalis (Fr.) M.J. Larsen. (Fig. 19)

Found in Chão da Ribeira, wrapping a completely rotten tree branch, IX–2023. MADJ-F-181.

Basidiome corticioid, tomentose and compact. Hymenium surface ferruginous brown with a paler

Fig. 19. *Tomentella crinalis* Pers. Hymenium.

Fig. 20. *Humaria hemisphaerica* (F.H. Wigg.) Fuckel. Ascocarp.

fimbriate margin, composed of sparse (1–4 per mm) up to 2 mm long concolorous acute spines, which are darker towards the top. Spores brownish, 7–10 μm , globose and warted.

Ascomycota

Humaria hemisphaerica (F.H. Wigg.) Fuckel. (Fig. 20)

Fruiting bodies found in Fajã da Nogueira on soil under a canopy of *Quercus* spp. trees, either growing alone or gregariously and establishing colonies IX–2023. MADJ-F-211.

Apothecia rather large, sessile, goblet shape to cup shape, up to 1.5 cm wide, densely covered in stiff, pointed brown hairs which are longer at the margin of the apothecium. Hymenium from greyish to white, somewhat light reflecting. Asci 8-spored, spores ellipsoid, 20–26 \times 10–13 μm , with irregular warts.

Myxomycota

Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa (O.F. Müll.) T. Macbr. (Fig. 21)

This species was found in Ribeiro Bonito, present on practically all deadwood in the area and with colonies almost entirely covering the substrate, IV–2023. MADJ-F-124.

Fig. 21. *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* T. Macbr. Sporophores.

Sporophore whitish, shiny translucent, coral like, dissolving when touched. The individual branches of the sporophore are up to 0.4 cm high, either erect or branched, covered in small stems at the apex where the spores are produced externally. Spores globose, 10–15 μm .

Observations: Locally abundant slime mold, and possibly common in Madeira, peaking during summer and thus probably overlooked (LÆSSØE & PETERSEN, 2019:1647).

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